

Spotlight on ELIXIR-IT Evolution: A Ten-Year Journey

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ELIXIR-IT All Hands Meeting 2023 – Rome

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NEW YORK POST Page Six
LATE CITY FINAL

Pope gives God 2 weeks' notice
I'M OUTTA HERE, GUYS!

'Bap! Bap!' SEAL tells how

CHEL'YABINSK

METEOR OVER RUSSIA
Southern Ural Mountains
FEB. 15, 2013

At 9:30AM local time a meteor streaked across the sky generating a fireball 30 times brighter than the Sun, exploding 14 miles high with an impact of 440 kilotons

The resulting sonic wave impacted an area of 200 sq. miles

что черт возьми это было

nature
THE INTERNATIONAL WEEKLY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE

SKYFALL

The trajectory, origin and airburst behaviour of the Chelyabinsk fireball
PAGES 202, 203 & 204

TOPICAL ESSAY: CAN WE BEAT THE PARASITES?
ESSAY: CHANGING MINDS
ESSAY: TIME CAPSULE

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Yet, oblivious to the omens...

...three brave scientists were fulfilling their project that was over five years in the making...

Vol 447/24 May 2007

nature

COMMENTARY

Life scientists have in the past relied on physicists to build facilities such as the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble, France.

Laying solid foundations for Europe

European life-science infrastructure has been neglected for too long. The next generation of facilities needs better coordination and community support, argue **Iain W. Mattaj** and **Glauco P. Tocchini-Valentini**.

Da: apweiler <rolf_apweiler@gmail.com>

Oggetto: Re: elixir?

Data: 29 novembre 2007 alle ore 10:52:26 CET

A: Graziano Pesole <graziano_pesole@unimi.it>

Cc: Rolf Apweiler <apweiler@ebi.ac.uk>, Dominic Clark <clark@ebi.ac.uk>

Rispondi a: apweiler@ebi.ac.uk

Dear Graziano,

I cc this email to Dominik Clark here at EBI. He can tell you a bit more about Elixir.

Cheers

Rolf

Dear Rolf,

do you know about the ELIXIR project about the proposal for an infrastructure for biological information? I wonder if we can join the partnership in some way..

best regards,
graziano

Highlights 2013-17

Observer

2013

2014

2015

2016

2017

2013

- ELIXIR-IT JRU established with Prof. Pesole as director (HoN)
- First Node Application with **eight data services, compute, training.**

2014

- ELIXIR Consortium Agreement enters into force.
- Italy joins as "Observer".
- Prof. A. Tramontano appointed scientific member of the ELIXIR Board
- ELIXIR-IT joins the **service registry** (later bio.tools) effort.
- LTec group established.

2015

- First four ELIXIR-IT **training events.**
- ELIXIR-EXCELERATE kick-off in December, limited participation from Italy due to still being an ELIXIR observer.

2016

- Italy becomes **full member** of the ELIXIR Consortium Agreement.
- First ELIXIR-IT branded compute service: ELIXIR-IT HPC@Cineca.
- First Train-the-Trainer event

2017

- Mint (as part of the IMEx Consortium) and MobiDB (as part of InterPro) enter in the first batch of **ELIXIR Core Data Resources.**
- ELIXIR-IT mirrors ELIXIR organising its activities in **platforms and use-cases** (later **communities**)
- 174 Tools and Databases maintained by ELIXIR-IT members are now in bio.tools.
- ELIXIR All Hands held in Rome.
- Prof. R. Casadio appointed scientific member of the ELIXIR Board

Highlights 2018-22

- 2018**
- New Node Application submitted to the Hub and approved by the ELIXIR Board. It reflects the changes in the organisation of ELIXIR-IT since its establishment (e.g. new members and services).
 - The new **SDP has 47 services + Training.**
 - ELIXIR-IT industry starts its activities.
 - ELIXIR-IT adopts a QM policy for selecting ELIXIR SDP services.
 - CNR-Biomics project awarded to ELIXIR-IT (14.5 M €)

- 2019**
- ELIXIR-IT participates in 14 ELIXIR impl studies / commissioned services.
 - First ELIXIR-IT industry event held in Milan.
 - 36 events organised (mostly training) by the Node.
 - Prof. S. Tosatto appointed lead of the ELIXIR Data Platform
 - ELIXIR-IT has an extra platform: integrative omics providing omics data generation services.

- 2020**
- COVID year ☹️, several events cancelled, and many more moved online.
 - ELIXIR-CONVERGE.
 - ELIXIR Converge WP9 -> COVID Data Portal Italy online towards the end of the year.

- 2021**
- SDP update, **ELIXIR-IT provides 68 services + Training.**
 - BY-COVID project
 - ML focus group publishes DOME Recommendations.
 - ELIXIR-IT participates 24 Impl studies / Comm. Services.
 - **ELIXIR-IT identified as high-priority infrastructure in the first PNIR 2021-27** (National Plan for Research Infrastructures)

- 2022**
- **ELIXIRNextGenIT** grant (~18M) awarded (RRF funds) in the RI Call.
 - For the first time, a key role (Node Coordinator) works full time for ELIXIR-IT (made possible by ELIXIRNextGenIT).
 - Joined the GDI Project, embarking in the (complex) quest of creating a FEGA Node for Italy.
 - Joined the EuroScienceGateway Project to build Galaxy capacity across Europe.
 - Data handling and analysis **National Platform**, which proposal was led by ELIXIR-IT, selected for implementation at Human Technopole.

Organisation evolution: working together

Policy / Oversight
Coordination
Operation

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Services evolution: working together

68 Services + Training in SDP 2021 update (from 47 in 2018)

In 2024 we will work towards a new SDP update and a revision of our service QM policy to better align with ELIXIR service selection recommendations and principles.

Thank you...